
Work Ethics Compliance as Predictors of Administrative Effectiveness of Non-Teaching Staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined work ethics compliance as predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The study was guided by four research questions and four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design for the study was a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 2,268 non-teaching staff of federal Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The sample size of 340 non-teaching staff (15% of the population) was drawn for the study using simple random sampling technique. Two sets of questionnaires titled: Work Ethics Compliance Questionnaire (WECQ) and Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach alpha method which yielded coefficient value of 0.80 for WECQ and 0.85 for AEQ. Simple regression was used for data analysis. The findings of the study showed among others that work ethics compliance based on age, education level and experience is positive and significant predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. It was also found that work ethics compliance based on gender is positive but not a significant predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that professionals who are mature and non-professional who are experienced should be employed to man administrative position and influence management to avoid employing administrative staff who have no interest in the job and are not ready to stay on the job.

Keywords: Work Ethics, Compliance, Administrative Effectiveness, Age, Gender, Educational Level and Work Experience

Introduction

Every organization puts in place measures to regulate the behaviour of members of staff. One of the measures to guide the actions and behaviours of staff in polytechnics is work ethics. It is the expectations of teaching and non-teaching staff to adhere to work ethics in discharging their duties on a daily basis. Work ethics is the guideline that specific expected behaviour and practices in an organization. Epelle, Alabere and Tamunomiebi (2023) defined work ethics as the moral principles, rules of conduct or special control mechanism that govern the actions of members of an organization. They added that in education system, work ethics is a set of moral principles and values that govern members of staff, which they are bound to observe. Work ethics define good or bad behaviour in the workplace. Work Ethics is described by Oriji (2023), as set of principles and values that guide organizations in their decisions, programmes and policies. Adinna and Okafor (2023) asserted that in a school setting, ethics is a terminology that represents work attitude and discipline. The authors added that it comprises behavioral specifications and institutional norms that form the collegiality of the school. Every member of staff is expected to exhibit total compliance to work ethics of an organization.

Compliance is a state in which something is in accordance with established guidelines, specification or legislation. Shindika and Chetani (2019) opined that compliance is adhering to established norms, which take the form of external laws, internal policies, and ethical values. Values depend on the organization, but can take the form of things like reputation and employees' personal ethics and goals. In essence, norms are rules. Ethical compliance is the practice of norms and values by employees of organizations based on expectations of society. A minimal ethical compliance would exist in the organizations by the differences in the awareness levels on workplace ethics and it revealed that once the employees are conscious of ethics at workplace, they are less affordable to comply with ethical practices of organization (Bulo *et al.*, 2020). Compliance to work ethics constitute a big challenge in the government sector, especially tertiary institutions. This manifests in absenteeism, lack of commitment in carrying out assignment, delayed or abandoned work. Thus, the degree to which employees comply with either covert or overt expected organization behaviour depends largely on the degree of awareness of what is acceptable behaviour in the first place. The degree of effectiveness of the non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, South East States like others will depend on among other factors on their demographic variables such as age, gender, years of job experience and educational level.

Age is the number of years that one has lived. Age is likely to affect the way that staff think and behaviour in the workplace. Amegayibor (2021) stated that as a person grows older, his or her feeling of responsibility and behaviour matures as well. Age could change how staff act in tertiary institutions. As non-teaching staff become older, they may likely exhibit more acceptable behaviour in the workplace. Ogun, and Okubokeme (2024) revealed that age bracket significantly influences ethical compliance amongst employees. Thus, age was considered as moderating variable in this study.

Gender is the patterns of behaviour, roles and expectations associated with being males or females. According to Igbolie, Obikeze, Ifejiofor and Muokwue (2021), gender is the state of being male or female in relation to the social and cultural roles that are considered appropriate for men and women in any society. The social and cultural expectations could influence work ethics compliance among male and female non-teaching staff. Ogun and Adigwe (2020) noted that gender had no bearing with ethical compliance levels amongst employees. On the contrary, Goel (2018) reported that there is significant difference in perception of work ethic compliance between men and women. Furthermore, Goel asserted

that men consider work ethic compliance as very essential, whereas female gave more consideration to paying fair wages and taking care of health and safety. On the other hand, Bordbar et al (2025) indicated compliance with work ethical codes was higher among females compared to males. Therefore, gender was considered as moderating variable in this study.

Education level could play essential roles in influencing work behaviour. Staff who have attained high level of education learn more about morality and ethics. One of the goals of higher education is building character. There is high tendency for staff to get enlightened about right and wrong behaviour as they further their studies. Higher level of education results in staff having more egos and at the same time greater expectations on the part of the parents and public for more ethical conduct in the workplace. Ogoun, and Okubokeme (2024) reported that work ethical compliance amongst employees was significantly dependent on education level. Also, Indah and Purnama (2024) noted that educational level had a positive influence on compliance to work ethics. Thus, educational level was considered as moderating variable in this study.

Years of job experience is the period in an individual has worked for an organization. Years of job experience could opportunity to members of staff to acquire practical knowledge of work ethics and perhaps comply to them. Similarly, Ochonma et al (2018) asserted that job experience leads to the accumulation of relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities that might enable managers behave well in the workplace. Otu, Ita, Oyamaand Uchegbue (2022) which indicated that the numbers of years in administrative position could increase the accumulation of knowledge and compliance to work ethics. Bordbar et al (2025) years of job experience had significant association with compliance with work ethics. In the same vein, Indah and Purnama (2024) noted that work experience had a positive influence on compliance to work ethics. Thus, years of job experience was considered as moderating variable in this study.

Some non-teaching staff tend to exhibit undesirable behaviour such as lack of dedication to work, lateness to work, absenteeism and other forms of misconducts in Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. There are some administrative staff who seem to divert some educational facilities provided for institutions development into private use, mismanage funds, disregard for standards and violate work rules among others. It is in this regard that the study finds it necessary to determine the extent work ethics compliance predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate work ethics compliance as predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the extent:

1. work ethics compliance based on age predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
2. work ethics compliance based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
3. work ethics compliance based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
4. work ethics compliance based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does work ethics compliance based on age predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does work ethics compliance based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?
3. To what extent does work ethics compliance based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?
4. To what extent does work ethics compliance based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Work ethics compliance based on age predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
2. Work ethics compliance based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
3. Work ethics compliance based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
4. Work ethics compliance based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The area of the study was South-East States Polytechnics in Nigeria. The choice of the area of the study was informed by the high value placed on education by the government of the South-East States. This high value on education indicates that most of the states in the zone are among the educationally advantaged zones; this is indicated by the federal, state government and privately owned tertiary institutions in the zone. The population of the study comprised 2,268 non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The sample of 340 non-teaching staff (that is, 15% of the population) was used for the study. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. Stratified sampling technique was used to stratify the non-teaching staff into different stratum where 15% was drawn for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw non-teaching staff from each polytechnic.

Two sets of questionnaires titled “Work Ethics Compliance Questionnaire (WECQ)” and “Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ)” were used for data collection. WECQ had 20 items structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. AEQ had 20 items structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The face validation of the instruments were determined by three experts (two in the area of Educational Management and one in the area of Measurement and Evaluating) all from the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Their comments were considered and used in modifying the instruments for final data collection. The reliability of the instruments was established through Cronbach alpha method. The overall reliability coefficients obtained, WECQ was 0.80 and AEQ was 0.89.

The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of six research assistants. Out of the 340 copies of the instruments administered to the respondents, that is 328 (96%) copies of the instruments were correctly filled and returned, while 12(4%) copies of the instruments were either misplaced or not correctly filled. Simple regression was used for data analysis. In answering the research questions, the regression coefficient rule suggested by Stephen (2017) was used for judgement as thus:

Negligible	0.00 - 0.19
Low	0.20 - 0.39
Moderate	0.40 - 0.59
Substantial	0.60 - 0.79
Very High	0.80 - 1.00

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does work ethics compliance based on age predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on age as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β
Constant	33.112	6.914	
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Age	.572	.304	.541
R	.541		
R ²	.445		
Adj. R ²	.397		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that work ethics compliance based on age moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .551$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .445, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 45% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics compliance based on age of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .397 indicating that 40% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics compliance based on age). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics awareness based on age is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .541$) showed that work ethics compliance based on age is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. This is an indication that increase in the age of staff based on the level of compliance lead to .541 (54%) increase in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: To what extent does work ethics compliance based on gender predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on gender as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β
Constant	15.883	4.116	
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Gender	.327	.215	.311
R	.311		
R ²	.218		
Adj. R ²	.208		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that work ethics compliance based on gender lowly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .311$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .218, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was slightly strong. This implies that 22% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics compliance based on gender of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .208 indicating that 21% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics compliance based on gender). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics compliance based on gender is slightly strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. However, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .311$) showed that work ethics compliance based on gender is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The positive prediction of staff gender and administrative effectiveness means that the administration of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria does not depend on gender of the staff. Hence, staff gender based on the level of compliance explained .218 (22%) of the variance in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Thus, the implication is that administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria would not depend on whether the staff is a male or female.

Research Question 3: To what extent does work ethics compliance based on educational level predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on educational level as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β
Constant	28.168	6.172	
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Education Level	.588	.305	.585
R	.585		
R ²	.452		
Adj. R ²	.413		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that work ethics compliance based on educational level moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .585$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .452, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 45% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics compliance based on educational level of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .413 indicating that 41% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics compliance based on educational level). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics compliance based on educational level is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Also, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .585$) showed that work ethics compliance based on educational level is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: To what extent does work ethics compliance based on experience predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 4: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on experience as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β
Constant	36.129	6.606	
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Experience	.597	.338	.575
R	.575		
R ²	.512		
Adj. R ²	.483		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 indicated that work ethics compliance based on experience moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .575$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .512, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 51% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics compliance based on experience of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .483 indicating that 48% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics compliance based on experience). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics compliance based on experience is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .575$) showed that work ethics awareness based on experience is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The positive prediction of staff experience and administrative effectiveness means that the more years in the service, the more effective the staff in the administration of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Hypothesis 1: Work ethics compliance based on age do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 5: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on age as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	33.112	6.914		8.144	.000
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Age	.572	.304	.541	12.603	.000
R	.541				
R ²	.445				
Adj. R ²	.397				
F	9.083				

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .541, while the r² is .445 and the adjust r² is .397/ The F-ratio associated with regression is 9.063 the t-test is 12.603 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on age do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on age significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Work ethics compliance based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 6: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on gender as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	15.883	4.116		1.135	.000
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Gender	.327	.215	.311	1.701	.000
R	.311				
R ²	.218				
Adj. R ²	.208				
F	3.502				.085

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 6 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .311, while the r² is .218 and the adjust r² is .208. The F-ratio associated with regression is 3.502, the t-test is 1.701 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.085) is greater than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, reject the null hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in

South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: Work ethics compliance based on educational level do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 7: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on educational level as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B	t-value	p-value
Constant	28.168	6.172		1.135	.000
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Educational Level	.588	.305	.311	1.701	.000
R	.585				
R ²	.452				
Adj. R ²	.413				
F	28.274				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 7 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is 0.585, while the r² is .585 and the adjust r² is .413. The F-ratio associated with regression is 28.274, the t-test is 19.976 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on educational level do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on educational level significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4: Work ethics compliance based on experience do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 8: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics compliance based on experience as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	36.129	6.605		29.057	.000
Work Ethics Compliance Based on Experience	.597	.338	.575	25.842	.000
R	.575				
R ²	.512				
Adj. R ²	.483				
F	33.711				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 8 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .575, while the r^2 is .512 and the adjust r^2 is .512. The F-ratio associated with regression is 483, the t-test is 25.842 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on experience do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics compliance based on experience significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Discussion

Findings on the extent work ethics compliance based on age predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria revealed that work ethics compliance based on age positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. The study indicated that most of staff was within the age bracket of 31-50 years. This means that most of the staff was not young in the profession. The authorities were guided by the fact that younger staff exhibit better management capabilities than older staff (within the age bracket of above 51 as the case in this study), since individuals tend to gradually disengage from active work with age. The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Nair et al (2017) found out that age has a positive and significant relationship with school administrators' effectiveness and that age to a little extent predict supervisors' effective secondary school supervisory practices. In the works of Zafer and Aslihan (2016), their findings revealed that teachers of age 31 to 40 years, 41 to 50 years old and above who responded to the survey had significantly higher scores in terms of their effectiveness. Their study showed that there is a difference between teachers' age in terms of their effectiveness, which indicates that older teachers are more effective than younger teachers. The significance of the result in this study is in agreement with the findings of Shindika and Chetani (2019) who noted that older aged staff comply more to work ethics than younger respondents in the world of work. In agreement with the finding of the study, Umar and Mohammed (2020) finding revealed that organizational age of respondents were the key determinant of their performance based on the compliance level in the prevailing organizational ethics in the organization.

Findings on the extent work ethics compliance based on gender predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria indicated that work ethics compliance based on gender positively but insignificantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a low extent. Gender has showed not to be a criterion for staff effectiveness in this study which means that staff effectiveness depends or is based on their capabilities and abilities. The finding of the study is in line with the finding of Wagbara (2017) who revealed that male principals were not significantly better in supervision than their female counterparts. The finding of the study is in disagreement with the finding of Uwa *et al* (2018) whose findings showed that female workers have the higher level of ethical compliance that leads to organizational profitability compare to their male counterpart. The difference and similarities observed in the studies could be attributed to the fact that individuals are judged based on what they can do, that is, their abilities, skills, capabilities and knowledge but not necessarily gender.

Findings on the extent work ethics compliance based on educational level predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

showed that work ethics compliance based on educational level positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. This finding is in line with the finding of Rahahle (2017) who disclosed that there was a moderately compliance from the respondents for the code of ethics which is based on the higher level of education. The similarities in the studies could be as a result of the employees' abilities in taking full responsibilities for every of their actions at work and anticipating in the changing conditions of the work to achieve the essence of the work.

Findings on the extent work ethics compliance based on experience predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria showed that work ethics compliance based on experience positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. The finding is in agreement with Ogbonna and Ebimobowei (2016) who revealed that compliance by the employees in terms of integrity, objectivity, honesty compliance positively and significantly affected the quality of services and performance of organizations. The finding is also in line with the findings of Bulo *et al* (2020) who revealed that level of ethics compliance is based on the experience of employees. Thus, employees with 5 years of working experience and above comply more to the work ethics than those with less than 5 years of working experience. The similarities found in these studies along the present study could be as a result of the gains and benefits derived from the experience which is the same in all sphere of work life.

Conclusion

The study showed that ethics serves as organizations' guide and encourage employees to practices good behaviour for the sake of improving their performance. Thus, the study concluded that work ethics work awareness and compliance based on age, gender, educational level and experience are positive and significant predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria except gender which is not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since experience significantly predicts administrative effectiveness, the study recommended that professionals who are mature and non-professional who are experienced should be employed to man administrative position and influence management to avoid employing administrative staff who have no interest in the job and are not ready to stay on the job.
2. There should be compulsory retirement plan for staff that are due to avoid poor administration in Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria by the State government.
3. Government should make retirement benefits and pension very certain to avoid manipulating age by civil servants due to fear of hardship at old age.

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